

Jualah on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Ju'alah contract on Islamic Financial Inclusion using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category saying the key " Ju'alah " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Ju'alah contract based on the journals that have been collected. The results of the research show regarding the implementation of the Ju'alah contract in Multi Level Marketing/MLM, in Rank Mobile Legend jockey service transactions, in Islamic Financial Institutions, in Bank Indonesia Sharia/SBIS Certificates, giving compensation in advance before implementing the Ju'alah contract, and the existence implementation of the Ju'alah agreement at this time. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Ju'alah contract, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Ju'alah; Islamic Financial Inclusion; Library Research

Introduction

The Ju'alah contract is concrete proof of the nobility of the Islamic religion which respects hard work and copyright. This concept is also in line with work professionalism which is highly valued by modern society; namely giving rewards according to the severity of the work load. Rewards or commissions which are common in al Ju'alah contracts are proof that Islam is a religion that is consistent and consistent in upholding the principles of honesty. The harmony of Islamic law is what makes Islamic rules always relevant to current developments. Apart from being in line with the principles of work professionalism, Al Ju'alah triggers and encourages many parties to compete in the field of creativity. Apart from that, this concept is also a form of ta'awun alal birri wa taqwa (mutual help in kindness and piety) to build an Islamic society that is modern, advanced, and has a noble personality in muamalah.

In everyday life, people often experience misfortune in the form of losing valuable and high-value items. The muamalah model in Islam is known as al Ju'alah. Not only that, in the modern world, the concept of al Ju'alah has developed into a basis for innovative activities and creativity with prizes. However, it must be noted that not all competitions with prizes are in accordance with the concept of al Ju'alah which is permitted in Islam. By understanding this concept, it is hoped that Muslims will be more advanced, productive and innovative in their work and charity.

of this research is to map research topics around the Ju'alah contract using Islamic Financial Inclusion library research. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding the Ju'alah contract, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Ju'alah contract, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Ju'alah contract is a promise or commitment (iltizam) to provide certain rewards (reward/'iwadh//ju'l) for achieving specified results (natijah) from a job. A party who promises to provide certain rewards for achieving specified work results (natijah) is called a jailer. Meanwhile, advanced is the party carrying out the sale.

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and compile the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is the Ju'alah contract. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about the Ju'alah contract on Islamic Financial Inclusion. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Ju'alah " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Ju'alah contract based on journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Study Relating to the Implementation of the Ju'alah Agreement in Multi Level Marketing (MLM)

study in previous research journals around implementation of the Ju'alah agreement in Multi Level Marketing (MLM), namely:

1. Products or services: In MLM, there are products or services offered to network members and consumers. This product or service must comply with the principles of Islamic law, which means it must not violate sharia provisions.
2. Price agreement: Before joining an MLM, network members must agree on the price they must pay to obtain the product or service. This price must be clearly set and must not contain elements of usury or other unlawful practices.
3. Commissions and bonuses: In MLM, network members can earn commissions and bonuses based on sales of products or services to consumers. These commissions can be considered rewards for the efforts made by network members in promoting and selling products or services to others.
4. Compensation structure: In MLM, there is a compensation structure that allows network members to earn commissions from sales made by other network members they recruit. The principle of the ju'alah contract still applies in this case, where network members who recruit new members will receive a commission based on sales made by the new member.

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Study Relating to the Implementation of the Ju'alah Agreement in Mobile Legend Rank Jockey Service Transactions

study in previous research journals around implementation of the Ju'alah agreement in mobile legend rank jockey service transactions, namely:

1. Price Agreement: The party who requires the services of a Mobile Legend rank jockey (hereinafter referred to as the "Service User") and the Mobile Legend rank jockey (hereinafter referred to as the "Service Provider") must agree on the price that will be paid by the Service User to the Service Provider. This price can be determined based on an agreement between the two or determined by the Service Provider.
2. Service Description: Service Users and Service Providers must ensure that they have a clear understanding of the services provided. Describe in detail the Mobile Legend rank that the Service User wants to achieve, the number of games that the Service Provider will play, and the expected ranking targets.
3. Terms and Conditions: Just like in general buying and selling transactions, Service Providers and Service Users need to determine the

terms and conditions that govern the transaction. This includes things like service terms, refund policies, and each party's responsibilities in the event of failure to achieve ranking targets.

4. **Payment:** After all service details and conditions have been agreed, the Service User must pay the specified price to the Service Provider. Payment can be made before the service begins or in the form of a part-time payment (for example, half up front and the remainder after the service is completed).
5. **Service Implementation:** The Service Provider will carry out Mobile Legend rank jockey services in accordance with the agreed agreement. They will play to achieve the ranking targets expected by Service Users.
6. **Reporting and Confirmation:** After the service is completed, the Service Provider must provide a report to the Service User containing information about the game results and whether the ranking target has been achieved. Service Users can then confirm whether they are satisfied with the services provided.
7. **Transaction Completion:** If the rating target has been achieved and the Service User is satisfied with the service, then the transaction is considered complete. However, if there is dissatisfaction or other problems, both parties must seek an adequate solution, such as negotiating a refund or additional games to achieve the desired target.

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Study Relating to Providing Benefits in Advance Before Implementing the Ju'alah Agreement

study in previous research journals regarding the provision of compensation in advance before the implementation of the Ju'alah contract, namely:

1. **Existence of agreement:** Providing advance compensation must be based on an agreement between the two parties involved. Both the seller and the buyer must clearly agree on the amount of consideration in advance and other terms regarding payment.
2. **Understanding regarding the use of the down payment:** The parties must agree on the use of the down payment. Will the deposit be refunded if the transaction is canceled or will it be considered as part of the overall payment?
3. **Compliance with sharia principles:** Providing advance compensation must comply with sharia principles which prohibit usury (interest) and gharar (uncertainty). Therefore, advance consideration should not be considered as a form of additional benefit obtained from the party providing the advance.
4. **Transparency:** All provisions regarding payment of upfront benefits must be explained in detail in the agreement or agreement agreed to by both parties. This will ensure transparency and avoid future conflicts.
5. **Fair use of advance consideration:** Payment of advance consideration must be fair to both parties. The amount of upfront compensation must be reasonable and not burden either party excessively.

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Study Relating to the Implementation of the Ju'alah Agreement in Islamic Financial Institutions

study in previous research journals around implementation of the Ju'alah agreement in Islamic Financial Institutions, namely:

1. Agreement between the Islamic Financial Institution and the business owner: At the beginning of the transaction, the Islamic Financial Institution and the business owner must reach an agreement regarding various aspects, such as the type of goods or services to be sold, the selling price, and profit sharing.
2. Purchase of goods or services: Islamic Financial Institutions purchase goods or services from business owners at an agreed price. This purchase was made using funds owned by the Islamic Financial Institution.
3. Sale of goods or services: After purchasing goods or services, the Islamic Financial Institution sells them back to the business owner at a pre-agreed price. This selling price can be higher than the purchase price as part of the profits will be shared between the Islamic Financial Institution and the business owner.
4. Profit sharing: Profits obtained from the sale of goods or services are shared between the Islamic Financial Institution and the business owner according to the initial agreement. This distribution can be based on an agreed percentage or in another form that is mutually agreed upon.
5. Payment settlement: The business owner will pay the Islamic Financial Institution according to the agreed selling price. Repayment can be made within a specified time or in the form of installments.

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Study Relating to the Implementation of the Ju'alah Agreement in Bank Indonesia Sharia Certificates (SBIS)

study in previous research journals around implementation of the Ju'alah agreement in the Certificate Bank Indonesia Syariah (SBIS), namely:

1. Identification of needs: Bank Indonesia Syariah (BIS) will identify the need for funds and financial instruments that can be channeled through SBIS. This may involve determining the amount of funds to be raised through the certificate, as well as the purpose for which the funds will be used.
2. Certificate offer: BIS will issue an offer to potential investors interested in purchasing SBIS certificates. This offering may include information regarding the characteristics of the certificate, including the amount, term, rate of return and associated risks.
3. Ju'alah Agreement: After the potential investor agrees to the offer, BIS and the investor will enter into a Ju'alah agreement. This agreement will govern the terms of sale of the certificates, including price, payment, and transaction settlement mechanisms.
4. Transaction implementation: After the Ju'alah agreement is signed, BIS will sell the certificates to investors. Payment will be made in accordance with the agreed terms, such as cash or through the financing mechanism stipulated in the agreement.
5. Transaction completion: Once payment is made, the transaction is considered complete and investors will receive an SBIS certificate as proof of ownership. BIS is responsible for providing investors with information and regular reports regarding their investment performance.

Mapping Research Topics using Literature Study Relating to the Existence of the Current Implementation of the Ju'alah Contract

study in previous research journals around the existence of the current application of the Ju'alah contract, namely:

1. Business and trade: Selling contracts can be used in buying and selling transactions between traders and consumers. For example, a seller offers goods at a certain price that includes the profit or profit desired by the seller. The seller and buyer agree on this price, and the sale and purchase transaction is carried out based on a sales contract.
2. Investment: Selling contracts can also be applied to investments. For example, someone wants to invest some money in a project or business. The party investing and the party running the project can use the sales contract to determine the percentage of profits that will be shared between the two.
3. Rental: In renting or renting, the sales contract can be applied in determining the rental price. The party who rents goods or property can determine the rental price by considering the desired profit. The renter can agree to the price or negotiate to reach a fair agreement.
4. Financial investment: In financial investment instruments such as bonds or sukuk, the sales contract can be used to determine the interest rate or profit that will be received by the investor. The issuer of the instrument offers an interest rate or return that is based on the expected profits from the project or investment supported by the instrument.
5. Sharia financing: Selling contracts are also used in sharia financing, such as murabahah financing. Murabahah is a sale and purchase contract in which the seller reveals to the buyer the cost of goods and the profit to be made. The buyer agrees to pay in cash or in installments at the agreed price.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 research topic mappings using literature studies related to the Ju'alah contract, namely: (1) Application of the Ju'alah contract in Multi Level Marketing/MLM; (2) Application of the Ju'alah contract in Rank Mobile Legend jockey service transactions ; (3) Providing compensation in advance before implementing the Ju'alah contract; (4) Implementation of the Ju'alah agreement in Islamic Financial Institutions; (5) Implementation of the Ju'alah agreement in the Bank Indonesia Sharia/SBIS Certificate; and (6) The existence of the current application of the Ju'alah agreement.

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